

A STUDY OF E-LEARNING: INDIAN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract:

Education has become a basic need of a human being. Every Individual must need to take education to become a self-developed person. Also, Modern Education provides promised employment which results in betterment of economy of a country. E-learning has provided a meaningful way of education. This study lights up on the aspects related to e-learning solutions which also includes the study e-learning pertaining to Education and society and the changes which are being faced in educational systems. This study then provides a summarization about the impact of e-learning on education and society.

Index Terms: e-Learning, e-Education & e-Society

1. Introduction:

The Concept of e-learning inclusion into an education begins with the teacher and the manner in which they teach. A simple explanation of the view is that the teacher is the final authority and source of knowledge. The problem for many teachers is transition of teaching in manner than accommodate the use of technology. Mining how they have previously been teaching with the use of technology which gives birth to e-learning. In e-learning, Technology is simply a mean that teachers may use in different ways in the new environment than can affect students and results. A teacher mulls to make use of technology needs to think how it may give a solution a problem of teaching they have within their learning environment. To overcome this problem in teaching use of e-readers could be the best way. It also overcomes the problem to a lack of textbooks. Another way could be helping students understand new ideas and concepts with the help e-learning platform. Many service organizations in society have used internet technology effectively to improve the quality or innovations in their services [1-7].

2. Education with an Integration of e-Learning:

E- Learning is a meaningful term that pertains to teaching, learning and the creating educational environment. Some examples of using technologies in e-learning classrooms are below:

- ✓ One-to-Many: Online classes. It includes lecture notes, quiz and assignment. The viewing of videos or other previously prepared material at a hub. The teacher visualizing data using a projector. The content may include PowerPoint slides. Distant learning Room or Video-conferencing, in which a teacher is broadcast live to a large number of rooms. The students can communicate to the teacher using video.
- ✓ One-to-One: Teachers examine individual student progress using a feedback program. Teachers check assignments, questions, and have office hours.
- ✓ One-Alone: E-reading tools with textbook (e-books).
- ✓ Student group presentations.
- ✓ Teacher Training: Teachers access training materials, exercises and take tests using online software.
- ✓ School Administration: Learning management system online.

Each of these described above can be carried out using various e-learning programs.

And using various technologies.

3. Impact of E-Learning on Education:

- ✓ E-learning makes the class rooms interactive which convert the School into learning environment.
- ✓ Interactive classrooms lead to funny way to learn.
- ✓ E-learning helps in active participation of students and teachers.
- ✓ The automate nature of E-learning provide animations for different concept which in turn helps in gaining knowledge better.
- ✓ E-learning and teaching also provide teachers with a large database of questions and also capable of helping to overcome the problem.
- ✓ Teachers can also upload content online; create question paper and examine student's performance.
- ✓ As ICT becomes integrated with the curriculum, it provides an audio-visual mode of learning that automatically develops the memory of the students.
- ✓ E-learning has different types of contents live animations, videos, self-explanatory diagrams, quizzes, eBooks and past year questions papers, all of which are regularly updated.
- ✓ It provides effective teaching and learning means in classroom for teachers and students with user-friendly GUI.

One of the best example of impact of e-learning on education in India is National Program on Technology Enhanced Learning (NPTEL), which is being funded and initiated by Human Resource Development (HRD) ministry. The six major engineering have streams been covered in this project for undergraduate level. The main purpose of NPTEL are, to make lectures in a video format for broadcasting that provides quality content to create e-learning material that would be make in such a way to meet the needs of engineering and other professional course across the country[8].

To make e-learning material available in the internet for the video lectures to compliment class room teaching. The NPTEL has developed curriculum based video courses. This is undertaken by seven IITs, IISc Bangalore as Partner Institutions (PI) and some other selected premier institutions as Associate Partner Institutions (API). In addition to this, a number of core courses common to all Engineering programs such as mathematics, physics, chemistry, management, Electronics, language etc, have also been included [9]. The main aim of the project NPTEL is to facilitate the competitiveness of industry in the global markets by improving the quality of education. Another objective of NPTEL is to make high quality learning material available to students across the country by using the advances in information and communication technology. The target group for this project consists of students and faculty of institutions offering undergraduate programs in India. A formal Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) between five IITs, Four IIMs and CMU established a Virtual Centre for Technology Enhanced Learning (VCTEL).

4. Social Impact of E-Learning:

The biggest impact of access to e-learning on various members of society could be significant. Apart from the improved skills, source of income and employment effects on graduates. Others impacts of education are improved health and prosperity, specifically among girls and women. This section on societal impacts briefly considers these types of impacts of education and then considers more closely the relationship between e-learning and society-specifically how the social content can affect the capacity of e-learning programs to furnish their potential benefits to all students. Social aspects such as living in a rural place, a person or a student speaking a different

language can all get access and use of e-learning application. E-learning model is getting popular in recent years in the name of in-line education [10 - 12].

One of the best impacts of e-learning on society is that of improved health. Because of this, one of aims of Development Goal Five regarding improving health is to promote girls who are going school, particularly primary school. As stated in the Goal (UNICEF 2011), "Educating girls for six years or more drastically and consistently improves their prenatal care, postnatal care and childbirth survival rates. Educating mothers also greatly cuts the death rate of children under five. Educated girls have higher self-esteem, are more likely to avoid HIV infection, violence and exploitation, and to spread good health and sanitation practices to their families and throughout their communities [13]. And an educated mother is more likely to send her children to school." Further impacts that specifically post-primary education has been to have in close reducing poverty, delaying girl's marriage, and consolidating decision making power. Secondary education plays a vital role in preparing for a long-term learning perspective. These are all the reasons why governments have been investing in compulsory primary school education and expanded secondary school education [14]. The education feed by the secondary schools may not be accessible to all parts of society or all areas of a country, hence e-learning has been found to affect this access to education. Research has shown that a lack in access to ICT created gap between countries, and an even larger gap subsist within countries between rural and urban areas, between women and men, and between poor and rich [15].

E-Learning has the ability to play a transitive role in a society. Culture also can play an important role affecting how technology and e-learning are adopted and adapted and how successful they actually are improving learning. The capable transformative role of e-learning often runs against educationalist choice for teaching in traditional ways that do not affect life in classrooms. Educators tend to use e-learning aspect in culturally familiar ways that may lower their effectiveness.

Language also can affect the e-learning programmes and specifically when learning software [16]. Learning materials and Internet is in a standard language in which many students and teachers are not good. In India for example, students switch from learning in their respective mother tongue in primary school to English as the language of first preference in secondary school. The students often took some English language classes in primary school, but many are not very well versed to learn into an English-only mode [17]. At the same time the most used language on the Internet is English, and most software and learning materials are in English. Students and teachers with limited knowledge of English may be marginalized. E-Learning can thus require to be becoming proficient in reading a second language before its capability can be met. However, e-learning and the Internet can also be a good motivator for students to learn English and other foreign languages popular on internet, is working to diminish the language barrier [18-21].

5. Conclusions:

We have now realized the critical importance of education for economic and social development. Schools and colleges are turning into e-learning rapidly. Many schools and colleges have started teaching e-learning programs. This paper is attempted to light upon a research on e-learning impacts and to know significant practices to add new and on-going e-learning programs. The teacher is important to thee-learning environment. For the students to have a successful e-learning experience the teachers would need to adopt new perspectives. These transitions may impact of the teaching skills; they will require new set of skills and abilities to prepare for e-learning

environment. The implementation of e- learning in an official setting requires further strategic planning. Changing the educational teaching through technology requires use of effective implementation tactics. Implementing any type of approaches that involves transition and differ how people work can overcome difficulties for an Organization. This paper has clearly provide the information as to how e-learning has helped the education and the society for the betterment of people and country which in turn helps to emancipate all in general.

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